

Politician, politics, political party and government behavior economy in Germany's economic development from the Merkel Era to the Scholz Era

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Abstract

This article examines the political and economic situation in Germany from the Merkel era to the Scholz era. It highlights the roles of politicians, political parties, and government behavior in the country's economic development. During Merkel's leadership, her government's labour reform was a major step in economic transformation. It adjusted the ecology of the labour market, reduced labour costs, and enhanced Germany's economic competitiveness. In the European debt crisis, Merkel's decisions, although controversial, safeguarded Germany's and the Eurozone's economic interests. Its shift in foreign policy, especially towards China, has also opened up new avenues for Germany's economic development. Under Scholz's leadership, however, the "traffic light coalition" faced problems. Each political party pursues its own interests, leading to deadlocks in economic decision - making. This has led to chaos and inefficiency in economic policies, as seen in conflicts over investment plans and energy policies. Politicians' personal interests are deeply intertwined with economic decisions, often sacrificing long - term economic development for short - term gains. The behavior of political parties and politicians has both aggravated Germany's current economic dilemma and holds the potential for recovery. Their actions have increased transaction costs during the Scholz era compared to Merkel's relatively stable tenure. Finally, the article emphasizes the significance of establishing four new disciplines – political or politics behavior economics, politician or statesman behavior economics, political party behavior economics, and government behavior economics. These disciplines can provide a more accurate analysis of economic decision - making mechanisms, improve policy effectiveness, help understand the origin and evolution of the economic system, support system optimization and reform, maintain economic stability and sustainable development, and strengthen social cohesion and political stability. Overall, understanding these political - economic aspects is crucial for the study of Germany's political economy and national governance.

Keywords: political party behavior economy · politician behavior economy · government behavioral economy · political behavior economy · political party behavior economics (政党行为经济学) · politician or statesman behavior economics (政客或政治家行为经济学) · government behavior economics (政府行为经济学) · political behavior economics (政治行为经济学) · institutional economics · traffic light coalition · Merkel era · Scholz era · Germany · economic policy · economic

I. Introduction

During the development process of Germany from the Merkel administration to the Scholz administration, the formation and evolution of the national economic governance system has been a core issue. In this process, the system is formulated by political parties, politicians and the government, and it is inevitably always linked to political factors. At the same time, the concept of institutional economics is relatively abstract and vague. In contrast, the economics of politician behavior (politician or statesman behavior economics), the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics), the economics of political behavior (political or politics behavior economics), and the economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can reveal the roots of German institutional economics more profoundly and clearly explain the rise and fall of Germany's economy under the leadership of the ruling party.

2. The Positive Contributions of Political Parties to the German Economy under Merkel's Leadership

2.1. Labor reform - A crucial step in economic transformation

When Merkel took office in 2005, Germany was facing severe economic difficulties. There were high fiscal deficits, persistently high unemployment rates, and the negative effects brought about by the overly developed welfare system were significant, such as rising tax rates, compressed corporate profits, and capital flight. The labor reform implemented by Merkel was a far-reaching measure.

This reform was a powerful continuation and expansion of positive policies during Schroeder era. By cutting corporate unemployment benefits and increasing retirement pensions, among other measures, it took over the high-welfare system. At the same time, the requirements for hiring and firing labor were relaxed. This adjustment fundamentally changed the ecology of the labour market. Under the new policy environment, enterprises were able to adjust their staffing more flexibly to market demand, effectively avoiding the cost burden brought about by redundant personnel. In addition, the government strengthened the skills training for employees. This not only improved the quality of the labor force, but also enabled the unemployed to have the ability to re-enter the job market, thereby increasing the labour supply.

From the data perspective, during the period 2001 to 2011, the average annual decrease in labor costs in Germany was 1.4%, while in the UK and France, they increased by 0.9% and 0.8% respectively. With this decrease in Germany and the increase in the other two countries, the competitiveness of German goods and services increased by 25%. German products became more competitive in the international market due to price advantages, laying a solid foundation for economic recovery and subsequent development. This series of labor reform measures clearly showed that the political party led by Merkel focused on long-term economic structural adjustment and competitiveness improvement in economic decision-making rather than short-term political interests.

2.2. Germany's role and economic strategic considerations in the European debt crisis

Under the dual impact of the global financial crisis and the European debt crisis, Germany played a key role in stabilizing the European economy. The European debt crisis, triggered by the Greek debt crisis, has plunged the economies of many European countries into a quagmire. Germany, under Merkel's leadership, actively participated in the Eurozone rescue plan, and its decisions reflected profound economic strategic thinking.

Merkel opposed the issuance of common bonds, but advocated implementing austerity policies in the recipient countries. Although this stance sparked widespread controversy within Europe, it was reasonable from the perspective of the overall economic interests of Germany and the Eurozone. Germany, together with the PIIGS (Portugal, Ireland, Italy, Greece, and Spain), belonged to the Eurozone and shared the currency. A debt default by PIIGS would seriously damage the creditworthiness of the euro, and these countries were also the main export markets for Germany. If their economies collapsed, Germany's exports would be severely hit. Merkel therefore urged recipient countries to implement austerity fiscal policies and reduce social welfare, urging these countries to carry out economic structural adjustments. Beginning in the second quarter of 2013, the Eurozone economy ended its quarter-on-quarter recession, and Germany's strategy began to show results. While stabilizing the European economy, it also safeguarded its own economic interests and further consolidated Germany's economic status in the European Union.

2.3. Adjustment of foreign policy to facilitate outward-oriented development of the economy

Merkel's shift in foreign policy has also created favourable conditions for Germany's economic development. It shifted from initially adhering to Germany's value-oriented diplomacy to pragmatic diplomacy, and this transformation was particularly evident in China-Germany relations. During her tenure, although there were some minor frictions between China and Germany, friendly cooperation was always the main theme of bilateral relations. Germany has established extensive and in-depth economic cooperation with China. Germany's high-end manufacturing products have gained broad development space in the Chinese market, and China has also provided a large number of investment opportunities for German enterprises. This pragmatic foreign policy has opened up new paths for the outward-oriented development of the German economy, enabling it to continuously expand opportunities for international economic cooperation and further promote the prosperity of the domestic economy.

3. The Performance of the Economy of Political Parties in Germany's Economy under Scholz's Leadership

3.1. The primacy of political party interests leads to a deadlock in economic decision-making

The Scholz government is ruled by the "traffic light coalition" composed of the Social Democratic Party (SPD), the Green Party, and the Free Democratic Party (FDP).

However, in the economic decision-making process, the negative effects of the economy of political party behaviour have become prominent. Each political party proceeds from its own narrow interests, resulting in a deadlock in economic decision-making.

The multi-billion-euro investment plan put forward by Habeck from the Green Party reflects the demands of environmentalists and emerging green industry interest groups represented by the Green Party. The Green Party hopes to promote the development and transformation of the green industry through large-scale government investment to achieve its environmental protection goals and consolidate its influence in government decision-making. However, this plan was vetoed by Scholz (from the SPD) and Lindner (from the FDP). Scholz of the SPD advocates increasing investment in the manufacturing industry and refuses to cut welfare in order to safeguard the interests of traditional manufacturing workers and social welfare recipients and ensure the support base of his political party. Lindner from the FDP proposed to suspend the green energy plan from the perspective of economic liberalism, taking into account the interests of traditional energy-related enterprises and ordinary enterprises, and worrying that the green energy plan might increase the burden on enterprises and affect free market competition. This economic decision-making model based on the interests of the political parties themselves makes it difficult for the government to reach consensus on economic policies internally. Every economic decision has become the focus of fierce competition among political parties, seriously hindering the effective formulation and implementation of economic policies.

3.2. The Chaos and inefficiency of economic policies under the competition of political parties

Continued competition among political parties led to a situation of chaos and inefficiency in Germany's economic policies. The economic transformation document put forward by Lindner was regarded as a "poison list" by the SPD and the Green Party because it contained a lot of content that damaged their interests, such as stopping new regulations, postponing the heating bill, abolishing climate policy regulations and subsidies, and cutting citizens' allowances. Such conflicting policy stances have made it impossible for the Government to form a unified and effective plan of action when dealing with economic problems.

At a time when the German economy has stagnated and is facing multiple problems such as high energy costs, sluggish exports, and fierce competition, the government should have quickly introduced a comprehensive economic reform plan. However, due to contradictions among political parties, policies have been capricious and lacking in coherence. For example, in terms of energy policy, the Green Party's radical plan to actively promote the development of green energy conflicts with the concerns of some members of the FDP and SPD, resulting in an indecisive energy policy. This not only affects the investment decisions of energy enterprises, but also makes it impossible to effectively solve the problem of energy price fluctuations, further increasing the production costs of enterprises, reducing the international competitiveness of German products, exacerbating the risk of economic recession, and making the German economy sink deeper into difficulties.

4. Economic performance stemming from politicians' behaviors in Germany's economy under Scholz's leadership

4.1. The Deep interweaving of politicians' personal interests and economic decisions

During the economic decision-making process of the Scholz government, the personal political interests of politicians are deeply intertwined with economic decisions. When formulating economic policies, politicians such as Habeck, Scholz, and Lindner primarily consider their own image and approval ratings within their parties and among voters.

Habeck put forward the National Investment Fund plan. His aim was to demonstrate his active role in promoting economic growth, thereby winning the recognition of Green Party supporters and voters who focused on economic development and consolidating his position on the political stage. However, Scholz and Lindner vetoed this plan also due to the weighing of their own political interests. Scholz needed to balance the interests of different groups within the Social Democratic Party to avoid losing support within the party by supporting plans that could affect traditional manufacturing industry and the welfare system. Lindner, on the other hand, had to safeguard the economically liberal views represented by the Free Democratic Party and prevent damage to its reputation within the party and among voters by supporting plans that would increase the financial burden or change the market competition pattern. The influence of politicians' personal interests on economic decisions has made the economic decision-making process complex and full of uncertainties, deviating from the optimal path based on the overall economic interests of the country and serving more the short-term political goals of politicians.

4.2. Damage to long-term economic development caused by politicians' pursuit of short-term interests

Under the complex economic situation, politicians in the Scholz government have shown more pursuit of short-term political interests. Faced with the problems of sluggish economic growth and budget deficits, there are serious differences among all parties regarding fiscal policies and economic stimulus plans. Politicians pay more attention to how to balance fiscal revenues and expenditures and meet the immediate interests of the groups they represent in the short term, while neglecting the long-term development of the German economy.

For example, under the current economic situation, Germany needs to fundamentally address issues such as economic structural adjustment, industrial upgrading, and sustainable development. Dealing with high energy costs requires long-term energy strategic planning, and enhancing export competitiveness requires continuous industrial innovation and upgrading. However, politicians lack a long-term vision of economic decision-making and focus only on short-term political gains and losses, resulting in economic policies lacking coherence and foresight. Such short-sighted behaviour has made the German economy face numerous challenges in the long-term development. Economic growth prospects are "between stagnation and snail's pace", making it difficult to break away from the current weak state and further harming the national economic interests.

5. The High correlation between the State of Germany's National Economy and the behaviors of political parties and politicians

5.1. The behaviors of political parties and politicians aggravating the economic dilemma

Germany's current economy is mired in stagnation or even recession, and the behaviour of political parties and politicians has played a crucial negative role in this. Disagreements and struggles within the government have rendered economic decisions unable to be implemented effectively, further worsening the economic situation.

Faced with problems such as high energy costs and blocked exports, the deadlock among political parties regarding economic policies, such as differences in investment plans, tax policies and welfare policies, has led to the government's inability to introduce effective countermeasures in a timely manner. For example, in terms of social welfare policies, the Social Democratic Party refuses to cut welfare while the Liberal Democratic Party hopes for adjustments. This contradiction has made it impossible to advance welfare reforms and has increased the financial burden. As far investment plans, the Green Party, the Social Democratic Party and the Liberal Democratic Party each stick to their own positions and cannot form an effective investment strategy to stimulate economic growth. The paralysis of economic decision-making caused by the behavior of political parties and politicians has made the German economy to sink deeper into difficulties, face the risk of contraction, and seriously affected the healthy development of the national economy.

5.2. The Obstacles and potential turning points of the behaviors of political parties and politicians to economic recovery

Although Germany witnessed unexpected economic growth in the third quarter, the prospects for economic recovery remain gloomy. The behaviour of political parties and politicians are both an obstacle and a potential turning point factors in this process. From the perspective of obstacles, the current mistrust among political parties and their obsession with their own interests have made it difficult to promote economic transformation and recovery plans. Disagreements over economic policies among all parties remain serious, and it is impossible to form a unified economic recovery strategy. However, from the perspective of a turning point, if under the pressure of the economic crisis, political parties and politicians can realize the severity of the problem, transcend their own interests, coordinate the views of all parties, and formulate policies that conform to the long-term development of the German economy, then there is still a possibility for the German economy to recover and get back on the growth track. This requires all parties to abandon the decision-making model dominated by the economy of political parties and politician behaviors, start from the overall interests of the country, and work together to solve economic problems, such as reasonably adjusting energy policies, stabilizing the manufacturing industry's development, strengthening the cultivation of emerging industries, and optimizing the social welfare system, so as to create favorable conditions for the future development of the German economy.

6. In terms of transaction cost

6.1. During the Merkel era:

6.1.1. Policy stability reduces transaction costs:

During Merkel's 16-year tenure, German politics was relatively stable. This stable political environment created favorable conditions for economic development and reduced transaction costs between enterprises and the government as well as between enterprises. For example, there was coherence in the formulation of economic policies. Enterprises could plan long-term investments and production and operations on the basis of relatively stable policies, reducing uncertainties and adjustment costs caused by frequent policy changes. The stable political environment has also enhanced the confidence of domestic and foreign investors in the German market, attracted a large amount of investment, further promoted the development of economic activities, and reduced information search costs, negotiation costs and so on in the transaction process.

6.1.2. Promoting European integration reduces external transaction costs

Merkel actively promoted the process of European integration and strengthened economic cooperation and coordination within the European Union. This enabled German enterprises to enjoy a more free trade environment in the European market and reduced transaction costs such as tariffs and non-tariff barriers in trade with other EU countries. For example, under the unified market rules, the circulation of goods, the flow of personnel and the flow of capital of German enterprises within Europe were smoother, reducing the complexity and costs of cross-border transactions.

6.2. During the Scholz era:

6.2.1. Differences within the governing coalition increase transaction costs

Scholz's governing coalition consists of the Social Democratic Party, the Green Party and the Free Democratic Party. There are differences in economic policies among the parties. These internal differences have led to low efficiency in government decision-making and increased policy uncertainty. Enterprises need to spend more time and energy adapting and adjusting when facing the constantly changing policy environment, thus increasing transaction costs. For example, in terms of energy policies, the Green Party advocates vigorously developing renewable energy, while the Liberal Democratic Party emphasizes the utilization of traditional energy more. Such differences have complicated the formulation and implementation of energy policies, and enterprises' investments and operations in the energy sector face greater uncertainty.

6.2.2. Changes in the international situation increase transaction costs

The current international situation is volatile. Events such as the Russia-Ukraine conflict have had a significant impact on the German economy. Germany's dependence on Russian energy has led to blocked energy supplies and a sharp rise in energy prices, raising production costs for companies. Meanwhile, the intensification of tensions in international political and economic relations have led to a rise in trade protectionism. German enterprises face higher trade barriers and market access restrictions in the international market, increasing their export costs and market expansion costs.

7. The Significance of Establishing Four New Disciplines, such as the economics of political party behavior, etc. for Germany

7. I. Level of economic decision-making and policy-making

7.1.1. Precise analysis of economic decision-making mechanism

In the process of economic decision-making in Germany, previous analyses from the perspective of institutional economics often overlooked the complex political behavior factors behind it. The four disciplines, namely the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics), the economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics), the economics of government behavior, and the economics of political behavior (political behavior economics), can dig deeper into the political driving forces behind decisions. For example, when formulating energy transition policies in Germany, the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) can reveal the different tendencies of various political parties regarding energy policies based on their own concepts and voter bases (for instance, the Green Party emphasizes environmental protection concepts to attract environmentalist voters, while the Christian Democratic Union may take into account the interests of energy enterprises and economic stability). The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can study how individual politicians weigh the interests of all parties in energy transition decisions for the sake of shaping their personal political images or advancing their political careers, such as making decisions on resource allocation between traditional energy enterprises and renewable energy enterprises. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can analyze the behavior patterns of government departments in the process of implementing energy policies, including how to coordinate the interests and actions among different departments (such as the Ministry of Economy and the Ministry of Environment). The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can explain the background of formulating energy policies from a broader political environment perspective, such as Germany's political commitments in international climate agreements and the pressure of domestic political public opinion. Such in-depth analysis helps Germany understand the formation process of economic decisions more accurately.

7. 1.2. Improving the scientific nature and effectiveness of economic policies

The scientific nature and effectiveness of Germany's economic policies are crucial for its stable economic development. Through the research of these four disciplines, a comprehensive evaluation of the policy formulation and implementation process can be conducted. Taking Germany's industrial policies as an example, the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) can analyze the support tendencies and policy propositions of various political parties for different industries (such as manufacturing and service industries), helping the government to comprehensively consider the opinions of all parties when formulating industrial policies. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can study the personal interest considerations of politicians in formulating industrial policies, such as influencing the policy direction in order to obtain the support of specific industrial groups. By identifying these behaviors, policies can be corrected.

The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can examine issues such as the administrative efficiency and the rationality of resource allocation in the implementation process of industrial policies. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can study the impact of international political and economic competition (such as competition with other countries in the manufacturing field) and domestic political games (such as differences in the demands of different regions for industrial layout) on industrial policies. In this way, Germany's industrial policies can be made more scientific and reasonable, and the effectiveness of policy implementation can be improved.

7.2. Level of construction and improvement of the economic system

7.2.1. Deeply understanding the origin and evolution of the economic system

Germany's economic system has been formed in the long-term interaction among politics, economy, and society. These four new disciplines can help Germany understand the formation of the economic system from the source. For example, from the perspective of the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) regarding Germany's social market economy system, different political parties have played different roles in its establishment and development. The Christian Democratic Union may emphasize market order and economic efficiency, while the Social Democratic Party may pay more attention to social fairness and welfare guarantees. The game and integration of these concepts have shaped the basic framework of Germany's social market economy system. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can study how the concepts and behaviors of key politicians influenced the direction of the system during its evolution, such as the contributions of politicians like Konrad Adenauer and Helmut Kohl to the construction of Germany's economic system. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can analyze the behavior patterns of government institutions in the process of maintaining and adjusting the economic system, such as the role of the German government in the reform of the financial supervision system. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can explain the evolution of the economic system from a broader perspective of political culture and historical background, such as the impact of the transformation of political concepts on Germany's economic reconstruction and institutional reform after the two World Wars.

7.2.2. Optimizing the design and reform of the economic system

Germany's economy is facing constantly changing internal and external environments, and continuous optimization and reform of the economic system is needed. These four disciplines can provide strong support for institutional reform. Taking the reform of Germany's tax system as an example, the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) can study the different positions and interest demands of various political parties on the adjustment of the tax structure (such as the reform of income tax, consumption tax and other tax types), providing multiple perspectives for the design of reform plans. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can analyze the behavior motives and strategies of politicians in promoting tax reform to prevent reform from being

distorted by personal interests or short-term political goals. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can evaluate the administrative ability and resource allocation requirements of the government in the reform of the tax collection and management system to ensure the smooth implementation of the reform. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can study the impact of international tax competition and domestic political public opinion on tax system reform, making the reform plan more in line with Germany's overall interests.

7.3. Level of economic stability and sustainable development

7.3.1. Maintaining the stable operation of the economy

The stable operation of Germany's economy is affected by multiple factors, among which political behavior factors cannot be ignored. These four disciplines can help Germany better cope with economic fluctuations. For example, during an economic crisis, the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) can study the choice tendencies of various political parties between fiscal stimulus policies and austerity policies and how these tendencies affect economic recovery. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can analyze the behavior decisions of politicians in responding to the crisis, such as taking emergency economic measures to stabilize public sentiment and their own political status. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can study the resource allocation and policy coordination abilities of government in crisis management, such as how to balance fiscal, monetary, and industrial policies to stabilize the economy. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can explain the transmission mechanism and coping strategies of the economic crisis from the perspectives of international political cooperation and geopolitical risks, ensuring that Germany's economy can operate stably during the crisis.

7.3.2. Promoting the sustainable development of the economy

Germany has always been committed to the sustainable development of the economy, including multiple dimensions such as economy, society, and environment. These four disciplines can provide comprehensive support for the implementation of sustainable development strategies. In terms of environmental policies, the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) can reveal differences in the positions and interest considerations of various political parties in promoting the development of the green economy and environmental protection policies, such as the Green Party's active promotion of the development of renewable energy and the concerns of traditional political parties about the costs of energy transformation. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can study the behavior incentives of politicians in the implementation process of environmental policies, such as strengthening environmental supervision in order to obtain the support of environmental protection organizations and meet the environmental protection demands of voters. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can evaluate the administrative efficiency and rationality of resource allocation of the government in the construction of environmental

infrastructure (such as sewage treatment facilities, garbage disposal facilities, etc.) and support for green industries. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can analyze the external pressures and opportunities of Germany's sustainable development policies from the perspectives of international climate agreements and the global environmental governance pattern, promoting the sustainable development of Germany's economy.

7.4. Level of social cohesion and political stability

7.4.1. Strengthening the public's understanding and participation in economic affairs

The degree of understanding and participation of the German public in economic affairs is crucial for the effective operation of the economic system and social harmony. These four disciplines can help explain to the public the logic of political behavior behind economic decisions and systems. For example, through the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics), the different roles and objectives of different political parties in economic affairs can be demonstrated to the public, enabling them to understand the diversity and dynamics of economic policies. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can reveal the personal interest considerations of politicians in economic decisions, allowing the public to understand the process of economic policy formation. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can display the working methods and responsibilities of government departments in economic management. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can explain economic phenomena from a broader political background perspective, such as the impact of international economic competition on Germany's domestic economic policies. In this way, the public's understanding of economic affairs can be enhanced, and their enthusiasm for participating in economic decision-making can be increased.

7.4.2. Maintaining political stability and social harmony

Economic issues are often closely related to political stability and social harmony. These four disciplines can help Germany identify and solve the factors in the economic field that can trigger political instability. For example, if the economics of political party behavior (political party behavior economics) finds that a certain political party implements unfair economic policies for its own benefit, which may lead to social dissatisfaction, the situation can be corrected by strengthening negotiation and supervision mechanisms among political parties. The economics of politician behavior (politician behavior economics) can prevent politicians from creating economic contradictions for their personal political interests, such as unreasonable resource allocation or tax policies. The economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) can ensure that the government exercises its power fairly and transparently in economic management, maintaining social fairness and justice. The economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) can analyze the impact of economic policies on different social groups from a macro political environment perspective, avoiding social division caused by economic policies and maintaining Germany's political stability and social harmony.

8. Conclusion

Essentially, in the process of forming Germany's governance system, the economics of politician behavior (politician or statesman behavior economics), the economics of political party behavior (political or politics party behavior economics), the economics of government behavior (government behavioral economics) and the economics of political behavior (political behavior economics) are the roots of German institutional economics. Politicians' decision-making motives based on personal interests and the pursuit of short-term benefits, as well as interest games and program inheritances among political parties, are constantly shaping and changing Germany's economic system. German institutional economics has been gradually formed and continuously developed largely on the basis of research on these politician, political party, government and political behaviors. Through in-depth research on the economics of politician and political party behaviors, we can better understand the formation, evolution and internal operating mechanism of Germany's economic system, and provide theoretical support and practical guidance for the sustained and healthy development of the German economy. Therefore, the establishment of the above four new disciplines is of great significance for the study of Germany's political economy and national governance.

In Europe and the United States, some politicians and economists frequently invoke new institutional economics to assess various countries, be it from theoretical, moral, or academic standpoints. However, a retrospective look at historical developments reveals a rather concerning trend. From the Merkel era to that of Scholz, with the passage of time and the shift in economic policies, Germany has witnessed an economic downturn. This clearly indicates that the very definition and scope of new institutional economics are flawed, giving rise to significant misperceptions among the general public and policymakers alike.

When the German government chose to embrace the new institutional economic policies under the Scholz administration, while abandoning the erstwhile policies of the Merkel era, the question of accountability looms large. Who, then, should bear the brunt of the ensuing economic decline or recession? It's also worth pondering whether a more contemporary economic system necessarily equates to a superior one under the new institutional framework. **Evidently, when it comes to the governance of a nation, new institutional economics proves to be theoretically tenuous. Not only does it mislead those engaged in economic research, but it also steers national governance astray.** After all, any country's institutional framework is crafted by individuals and institutions. In this light, political behavior economics, political party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and politician behavior economics can arguably be regarded as precursors or foundational elements of what is known as new institutional economics.

Therefore, it would be far more prudent for European and American countries and economists to explore the institutional and political economies of European and global nations through the lens of these behavioral economics perspectives, namely, political behavior economics, political party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and politician behavior economics. This approach might offer a

more nuanced and accurate understanding of the complex economic and political landscapes at play.

We can see that Germany is not a country with a market economy-oriented economic system, but a country with multiple economic sectors. In fact, a similar situation exists not only in the United States, the United Kingdom, Sweden, Italy, France, Russia, and China, but also throughout Europe and indeed on a global scale. **John Nash once said**, "A great economic theory needs more than 50 years to prove its significance." The author completely disagrees with this statement. It shows that when building the edifice of economic theory in the past, European and American countries lacked foresight and were unable to quickly construct a highly predictable and effective political and economic theoretical system to guide national governance or global governance.

From a military perspective, if a side with weaker military strength is about to go to war with a stronger side, and if the commander of the weaker side has no correct military theory to guide them and still needs to use a theory that will take 20 years in the future to verify, the weaker side will usually suffer a quick and crushing defeat. In the prevention and treatment of the COVID-19 pandemic that affected the whole world, if it takes a long time to test whether a medical theory and method are correct or not, many people will inevitably get infected and many patients may die. What's the point of such a theory? In fact, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the tragic situations in most countries around the world were as described above. However, doctors or pharmacists with great foresight should be able to formulate effective plans in the absence of specific drugs or treatment guidelines or expert consensus. They should be able to develop rapid and effective theories and methods for preventing and controlling the epidemic within dozens of minutes or a few days, quickly and effectively control the incidence rate, and quickly and effectively cure severe patients. If the treatment theory is correct, severe patients over sixty years old don't need ventilators and hormones. After taking the medicine, their symptoms can be reversed within 1 to 4 hours and they can finally be cured. The author of this article has experienced the whole process and neither himself nor his family members have ever been infected despite having contact with severe patients. The theories that are currently widely recognized but lacking foresight may turn out to be very bad theories even if they have been around for more than fifty years. For another example, in modern medical theories, the medical theory that clinicians recommend surgically removing tonsils when patients have severe recurrent tonsillitis has been a medical consensus for over a hundred years. In fact, this is seriously wrong, and patients will inevitably have lifelong sequelae. This indicates that some contemporary medical theories rarely possess foresight and instead reflect the inertia of clinical medical theories. For patients with severe tonsil infections who, according to the current expert consensus, require surgical operations, usually the author can cure them in just a few days without leaving any sequelae for the patients. The author has already proposed to establish a United Nations consensus to prohibit the implementation of tonsillectomy.

In other words, most economic theories nowadays lack basic foresight, which is why **John Nash once said**, "A great economic theory needs more than 50 years to prove its significance." In almost all countries around the world, when the president or prime minister changes, the so-called new institutional economic situation emerges, and in Germany, it is manifested in the change of the government led by the prime minister and the ruling party. This fully shows that this new institutional economy is presented to the world based on reflecting the political concepts of politicians, political parties, and the ruling party as well as their political behavior economics, political party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and politician behavior economics, and their behaviors are basically predictable in advance. However, it is inaccurate to express it merely in terms of new institutional economics. Obviously, the significant contributions that the emerging disciplines of political behavior economics, political party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and politician behavior economics will make to national governance worldwide are quite predictable.

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